

**A segmentation study
of Mexican consumers based on shopping centres' attractiveness**

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Abstract

Purpose – To identify shopping centre attractiveness dimensions from Mexican shopper point of view and then segment shoppers according to these perceptions of attractiveness.

Research methodology – Quantitative research: the data was collected through a survey given to 1500 regular shopping centre consumers from the Metropolitan Area of Guadalajara (MAG), Mexico. This research study was carried out from January to April 2010. Five of the largest shopping centres, including a lifestyle centre, a community centre, a regional shopping centre, and a small regional shopping centre participated in this research study voluntarily.

Findings – The attractiveness attributes of six shopping centres were identified through a factorial analysis: mall essence, popularity and promotional programs, personal service, recreational offerings, internal atmosphere, and external atmosphere. Also, a cluster analysis of these factors revealed three types of consumers with significantly different perceptions of shopping centres: serious, enthusiast, and basic. The outcomes were validated by a multiple discriminant analysis. Multiple discriminant results suggest that the dimension of popularity and promotion programs is the first to distinguished among segments followed by internal and external atmosphere.

Practical implications – From a managerial perspective, the study provides practical advice to managers in order to support their marketing and positioning strategies for their shopping centres focusing on a particular segment of consumers.

Originality/value – This study contributes to the body of research on shopping centre attractiveness and shopper segments by providing information regarding Mexican consumers' shopping perceptions.

Keywords: Shopping centres, attractiveness, segmentation, Mexican shoppers.

1. Introduction

Shopping centres and customer patronage have been a focus of much research in different countries in the last decade. The objective of this retail literature has been to identify how variables such as convenience, quality and variety of brands, price, among others, explain consumers' preferences. Today more than ever, consumers are exposed to many alternatives; thus retailers have to develop innovative strategies to maintain regular customers and attract new ones. In a recent study, D'Andrea (2010) argued that Latin America's retail landscape has experienced a modernization and increasing competitiveness in the areas of supermarkets, shopping centres and e-commerce. However, in Mexico, despite the constant growth of the shopping centre industry, the empirical research hasn't been proportional. According to a Colliers International report (2011), in recent years the number of shopping centres in Mexico has increased around 45% (2007-2008: 45%; 2008-2009: 51%, 2009-2010: 40%). At the end of 2010, the Mexican retail sector reported 550 shopping centres with 15,754,917 m² including power centres, fashion malls, outlets, community centres, regional centres, entertainment centres and lifestyle centres (Colliers International, 2011)

In this environment of shopping centre proliferation, the first concern for retailers and administrators is to understand shopper behaviour, preferences and motivations, and also to understand how shopping centre attractiveness could contribute to them. In order to develop the appropriate retail strategies and to clearly differentiate from the competition to retain existing consumers and appeal to new ones, the questions for shopping centre retailers and administrators are who are their specific shoppers and which shopping centre attributes are important to attract them.

The purpose of this paper is to contribute to the knowledge about Mexican shopping centre consumers. To this end, the present study aimed to identify shopping centre attractiveness dimensions from the point of view of the Mexican shopper and then segment shoppers according to these perceptions of attractiveness. To do this, a quantitative study was conducted; a survey was given to a sample of 1500 regular customers of shopping centres in the Metropolitan area of Guadalajara (MAG) from January to April 2010. Guadalajara is the capital of the state of Jalisco and is located in the central-west region of the country.

This metropolitan area has the second largest population in the country after the metropolitan area of Mexico City. The MAG comprises eight municipalities—Guadalajara, Zapopan, Tlaquepaque, Tonalá, Tlajomulco de Zuñiga, El Salto, Ixtlahuacán de los Membrillos y Juanacatlán—whose total population is 4,364,069 (INEGI, 2010). The state of Jalisco is considered a pioneer in the development of shopping centres; the first shopping centre in Latin America, Plaza del Sol, was opened in Guadalajara on November 25, 1969. The MAG has more than 40 shopping centres or malls with modern infrastructure, where a wide range of local, national, and international brands are sold.

Five urban shopping centres voluntarily participated in the study, representing a great variety in profiles according to the ICSC classification (2004): lifestyle centre, community centre, regional centre and small regional centre.

The methodology involved generating a scale to measure attractiveness via literature, discussion groups and a structured questionnaire, and validating it through a factor analysis. In addition, cluster and discriminant analyses were used to establish typologies of Mexican shoppers.

2. Shopping Centres' Attractiveness

According to Teller (2008), a shopping centre is attractive when it is preferable at different stages of the buying process. In addition, Anselmsson (2006) proposed that the impact of attractiveness could be reflected in the number of visits to the shopping centre, retention time and the amount of spending per visit. Thus, discovering what factors make a shopping centre attractive has been the object of studies since the 1960s. In these first studies, the distance from the consumer's home and the size of the shopping centre were the most significant factors explaining consumer preferences and behaviour in shopping centres. The first predictive model of this type was Huff's Gravity Model (1963), which predicts the attractiveness of a shopping centre as inversely proportional to the distance between the shopping centre and the location of its consumers, and directly proportional to its size. However, in studies conducted at the end of the 1970s and the beginning of the 1980s, other factors more oriented toward cognitive dimensions were added, leading to a multidimensional model that better predicts a shopping centre's attractiveness (Más Ruíz, 1999). These cognitive dimensions have evolved into the concept of shopping centre image,

which is related to the belief that consumer perceptions of shopping centre characteristics are more determinant of shopping centre selection than the characteristics themselves (Frasquet, Gil, and Molla, 2001). In this sense, Más Ruíz (1999) has provided 3 factors to measure shopping centre image: *shopping environment*, *variety and professionalism*, and *parking*.

In addition, some groups of researchers (Dennis, Marsland, and Cockett, 2001; Wong, Lu, and Yuan, 2001; Sit, Merrilees, and Birch, 2003) considered four basic components of shopping centre image in their studies: *merchandising*, *accessibility*, *services*, and *atmospherics*.

According to Sit et al. (2003), the first of these, *merchandising*, refers to the core of shopping centre activities. This dimension was measured in terms of the diversity of brands and categories, quality, and price. The *accessibility* of a shopping centre involves both internal and external aspects. Internal aspects involve the facilities, including the ease and comfort of access, circulation, and parking, among others. External aspects include the shopping centre's location in reference to its consumers. The third factor, *services*, refers to the 'augmented product' related to the knowledge and friendliness of the personnel, as well as the infrastructure of a shopping centre such as escalators and elevators, and amenities such as restrooms. Finally, the last of the big four attributes of shopping centre image, *atmospherics*, is made up of five items: ambience, colour, decoration, music and design.

Another contribution to the literature was the incorporation of a motivational aspect in understanding shopper patterns. Traditionally two types of consumers were identified: the economic/convenience shopper and the emotional/recreational shopper. Several studies have stated that the shopping centre has become a centre for social and recreational activities. In this sense Reynolds, Ganesh and Lockett (2002) have proposed *entertainment* as a dimension of shopping centre attractiveness. Subsequent empirical results have confirmed that the attractiveness of a shopping centre includes *entertainment* as a factor of considerable interest in consumers' perceptions of shopping centres (Sit et al., 2003; El-Adly, 2007; Rajagopal, 2009). Sit et al. (2003) defined *entertainment* as the group of amenities including general and special shows offered by the shopping centre. General amenities comprise restaurants, food court and cafes, movie theaters, and play areas for children. Special entertainment includes events such as cultural performances, fashion

shows, and Christmas parties. El-Adly's (2007) results added to the previous definition of *entertainment*, incorporating *promotional campaigns in the mall* and *availability of loyalty programs*, both of which are more related to shopping centre communication programs than to recreational offerings. And, different from previous research, El-Adly's (2007) results included attributes such as restaurants, food and cinemas, among others, in a factor called *diversity*.

As a conclusion of the above literature review, it could be said that there is no consensus about how many dimensions explain shopping centre attractiveness, or which items describe each dimension. However, there is a group of dimensions common to several studies that could be used to examine Mexican shoppers' perception of shopping centre attractiveness. The following table summarizes the incorporation of dimensions in the study of the perception of shopping centres through a selection of key studies in this area.

[Insert Table 1]

In sum, for this first part of the study the purpose has been to identify the dimensions of shopping centre attractiveness from the Mexican shopper's point of view. To that end, previous studies were collected and incorporated into a scale (see Table 5) including physical, cognitive and entertainment elements.

3. Consumer typologies of shopping centres

The studies about shopping centre attractiveness have been used to identify different profiles and typologies of consumers (Boederek, 1995; Dennis et al., 2001; Yavas, 2003; Martin and Turley, 2004; among others). These segmentations have been used to explain and describe consumer typologies using perceptions of attractiveness, motivations, behaviour, attitudes, satisfaction, etc.

According to the literature reviewed, two types of methodologies have been used to achieve the segmentation. One group of studies has employed a priori segmentation, using variables such as gender (Dennis et al., 2001; Martin and Turley, 2004; Anselmsson, 2006; Michon et al., 2008; Kuruvilla, Joshi, and Shah, 2009), age (Dennis et al., 2001; Anselmsson, 2006), or mothers and daughters (Martin, 2009). However, the usefulness of a priori

variables has been criticized; thus many studies have opted to incorporate other variables to explain behaviour, leading to the second methodology, post-hoc segmentation. The orientation of a post-hoc segmentation has been to classify shoppers according to what they do at the shopping centre, more than who they are (Ruiz, Chebat, and Hansen, 2004).

In post-hoc methodology, one of the most influential segmentations was made by Bloch, Ridgway, and Dawson (1994), who identified mall enthusiasts, traditionalists, grazers and minimalists using behavioural patterns in shopping centres. In this empirical tradition, Terblanché (1999) identified three types of shoppers: the functional shopper, the recreational shopper and the social shopper. Terblanché's segmentation was based on the perceived benefits that consumers enjoyed when visiting a shopping centre: functional, recreational, social and convenience benefits. More recently, Ruiz et al. (2004) used a consumer's activities in the shopping centre to elaborate a segmentation that recognized four types of shoppers: recreational, full experience, traditional and mission shoppers.

From another perspective, a group of researchers have considered for segmentation the importance of the centre's attributes (Boederek, 1995; Dennis et al., 2001; Frasquet et al., 2001; Reynolds et al., 2002; Sit et al., 2003; El-Adly, 2007), bringing attention to consumers' perceptions and how these perceptions could influence their shopping centre selection.

If we analyse these segmentations carried out across time and countries, UK (Dennis et al., 2001); Spain (Frasquet et al., 2001; Munuera Alemán and Cuestas Díaz, 2006); USA (Reynolds et al., 2002); Singapore (Ibrahim and Ng, 2002); Australia (Sit et al., 2003); Canada (Ruiz et al., 2004); Brazil (Da Costa Hernandez, 2005); Hungary (Millan and Howard, 2007); Arabian (El-Adly, 2007); Israel (Gilboa, 2009); it can be observed that certain types of consumers have been consistently identified, although with some variations in nomenclature, or in some cases with more detailed divisions within these segments (see Table 2).

A first segment is made up of consumers who are practical in their purchases and seek to satisfy their most utilitarian needs; this group has been called minimalist, serious or mission shopper. This segment only goes to the mall to get the products they planned to buy in advance (Ruiz et al., 2004), thus their perception of the shopping centre seems to be as a 'destination retailer' (Reynolds et al., 2004). A second group sees the shopping centre as a

place for socialization and entertainment; this segment has been named grazer, entertainment, recreational or relaxed shopper. The entertainment shopper places higher importance on the atmosphere of the shopping centre and its entertainment attributes (Sit et al., 2003). A third group of consumers is the traditionalist, also called basic, convenience or pragmatic shopper. This group is interested in the atmosphere and convenience of the shopping centre. They are fundamentally focused on purchasing activities, and they are not attracted to browsing, eating or consuming services (Bloch et al., 2004). Finally, a fourth type of consumer is the full-experience shopper, also named enthusiast and demanding. This group seeks a wide range of activities in the shopping centre, such as shopping, entertainment and socialization, and thus has perceptions based on a greater number of factors (El-Adly, 2007).

[Insert Table 2]

As a result of the literature review, the present study has as a second objective to develop a typology of Mexican shoppers based on their perceptions of the attractiveness of the shopping centre.

4. Methodology

In this study, four types of shopping centres were studied. Following the classification proposed by the ICSC-U.S. (2004), the shopping centres evaluated belonged to the categories of open-air centres and malls. Within the first category, open-air centres, there were two types, lifestyle centre and community centre. In the second category, malls, two different types were considered, regional centre and small regional centre (see Table 3).

[Insert Table 3 here]

This study was conducted in two phases. The first phase involved qualitative research, designed to explore patronage behaviour and purpose of visit, and to look for components that shoppers perceived to be important for shopping centre attractiveness. In order to select appropriate items, two discussion groups were conducted. Both groups represented different ages (>18 years old) and gender (male and female). All of the participants were regular shopping centre consumers. From the discussion group and previous literature, a five-point Likert scale of 28 items was created. The scale was pre-tested with a convenience sample of 150 shopping centre consumers.

For the second phase, a survey was collected from a sample of 1500 shoppers. People who were visiting one of the five shopping centres were invited to respond to the questionnaire (see Table 3).

Using data supplied by administrators of the shopping centres about the regular consumer, which affirmed the importance of women in the total group of shopping centre consumers and the growing incorporation of men as shopping centre consumers, a proportion of 80% female and 20% male was decided upon. Additionally, a schedule of days and hours was generated to ensure that all times of the day/evening and of the week were represented. The application of the questionnaire was carried out in areas of flow within the shopping centres, such as movie theatres, food courts, rest areas, and other areas with a lot of pedestrian traffic.

In the final sample of survey respondents, 52.6% of participants were age 18 to 24 years, 22.4% were 25 to 32 years, 9.6% were 33 to 39 years, 7.9% were 40 to 47 years, and 3.7% were 55 years or older. Regarding marital status, 66.6% of the participants were single, 30.2% married, 2.8% divorced and 0.4% widowed. A total of 33% of the participants had children and 67% didn't. In addition, 56.5% were university graduates, and the rest possessed varied levels of preparation from high school diplomas to middle school education or less.

[Insert Table 4]

The instrument of measurement was a questionnaire divided into three sections (see Table 4). The first section included questions aimed at identifying the participants' favourite shopping centres, the most visited centres, the frequency of visits, the main purpose for visiting a shopping centre, and frequency of consumption. The second section contained a five-point Likert scale with 28 items to measure consumers' perception of shopping centre attractiveness. Finally, the third section included sociodemographic variables: gender, age and marital status, number of children, level of schooling, occupation and area of residence.

5. Results

5.1 Shopping centre attractiveness factors

To obtain the dimensions that make up the attractiveness of a shopping centre in the minds of Mexican consumers of the MAG, a factorial analysis was applied to the 28 items evaluated by the survey respondents. As a result of this analysis, six factors were found which explained 60.04% of the total variance of the data. In order to validate the measurement instrument, Cronbach's alpha was calculated for the 28 items and a value of 0.937 was obtained. Also, as can be seen in Table 5, when calculating Cronbach's alpha of the items within each factor, all of the values were greater than 0.70, except the last factor (0.669). These results indicate that the measurement instrument showed a high internal reliability.

Table 5 presents the results of the exploratory factor analysis with varimax rotation; the factors were identified based on the items that compose each of them, considering their factor loadings. Consistent with the theory previously reviewed, the dimensions that explain the perception of a shopping centre are grouped into factors related to *mall essence, popularity and promotional programs* of the shopping centre, and *personal service*. All of these are weighted toward the cognitive more than the physical elements of the shopping centre. The three remaining factors are located more in the physical environment, specifically the *internal atmosphere* and the *external atmosphere* of the shopping centre and its *recreational offerings*.

The factor that we have called *mall essence* is that which explains most of the variance (37.62%), and the items that contribute to it are *variety of brands, diversity of types of businesses, fashionable brands offered, prestigious brands offered, level of price, and quality of offerings*. *Popularity and promotional programs* include items such as *organization of special events, shopping centre advertising campaigns, promotional events and sales*, among others. In *personal service* the most important items are *training of personnel*, followed by *friendliness of personnel* and *number of available personnel*. *Internal atmosphere* is mainly composed of *ease of circulation in the shopping centre, illumination and decoration*. In the factor of *recreational offerings*, the items that contribute most are *food offered in the food court, diversity of restaurants and areas of entertainment for children*. Finally, the *external atmosphere* includes classic physical items

such as *location of* and *access to the shopping centre*, *available parking* and *perceived security*.

[Insert Table 5]

5.2 Shopping centre attractiveness segmentation

In general terms, shopping centre consumers in the MAG are frequent consumers who go to a shopping centre at least once a week (38.3% from three to four times per month and 27.9% from five to eight times per month). Their three main purposes for visiting a shopping centre are to shop (81%), entertainment (go to the movies 71%, and eat at restaurants or at food court 62%) and socialize (meet with friends 35% and have fun with the family 24%).

The objective of this second part was to classify shopping centre consumers of the MAG. To achieve this, a cluster analysis was carried out using the evaluation given to the factors identified above as building blocks of the attractiveness of shopping centres. The number of segments obtained was determined through a hierarchical cluster, taking as a cut-off point the moment that the distances between the cluster values became relevant (Norusis, 2008). From this analysis, three segments were identified with the following sizes: segment 1 = 330 individuals (25.9% of the total); segment 2 = 448 individuals (35.2% of the total); and segment 3 = 495 individuals (39.8% of the total) from a sample of 1273 valid questionnaires, once those that were incomplete or lost had been eliminated. The differences among the means of the three segments were significant for all of the factors considered ($p = .000$) (see Table 6).

[Insert Table 6]

Table 6 shows the difference between shopper segments related to shopping centre attractiveness factors. Demographic characteristics, shopping centre activities, preference and frequency of consumption are summarized in Table 7. Each of these shopper segment descriptions are discussed in turn.

[Insert Table 7]

Serious shopper

The serious shopper (segment 1) makes up 26% of the sample. High scores to personal service and internal/external atmosphere distinguished this segment; these are the aspects that received the least criticism from this segment. The serious shopper is especially critical of attributes related to mall essence, promotions and recreational offerings of the shopping centre. With respect to the demographic configuration, the serious segment is made up of men aged 48 or older. In addition, the selection of favourite shopping centres was found among the statistically significant results: serious consumers expressed their preference for regional centres. The most complete mix of brands and categories describes regional centres. The frequency of visits to shopping centres was also found to be a significant variable in describing the segments of consumers. The serious segment was found to be moderate consumers, visiting between 3 and 4 times per month.

Enthusiast shopper

The second segment, enthusiasts, corresponds to 35% of the sample. This segment gave the highest scores to all of the evaluation factors of the shopping centre, demonstrating their ease of acceptance of the offerings of the shopping centre in comparison with others. The majority of enthusiast shoppers are adult men and women 33 to 47 years of age, and they are the most frequent shopping centre visitors, going more than 5 times per month (“5 to 8” and “more than 8”). According with their evaluation, they prefer lifestyle centres, which have the more exclusive and modern offering of brands, dining and entertainment areas.

Basic Shopper

The basic shopper, the largest segment of consumers (39% of the sample), is oriented to the mall essence, a factor related to variety, prestige, level of prices, quality of offerings, and personal service. The basic shopper gave very low scores to all of the rest of the dimensions related to attractiveness. With respect to the demographic configuration, the majority are women aged 18 to 32 years. They prefer community centres related to functional or physical convenience, and they visit shopping centres least frequently, 1 to 2 times per month.

5.3. Validation of shopper segmentation

As can be observed previously, there are significant differences among the segments in attractiveness dimensions, demographics and behavioural variables. Therefore, a discriminant model can be constructed which can be used to validate the segmentation and identify the most significant variables to predict segment membership.

Discriminant results

The discriminant model is composed of two discriminant functions; both were significant ($p < 0.001$). The discriminant function 1 explains 52.5% of the variance in the three segments and the discriminant function 2 explains 47.5% of the variance. Using the cross-validation process, the discriminant model classified correctly 97% of cases in both samples (see Table 8). The global adjustment, according to Noble and Schewe (2003), determines whether these results exceed the percentage of correctly classified individuals that would have been obtained if all of the observations had been assigned to the segment with the highest probability of occurrence ($C_{pro} = 34.2\% < C_{max} = 38.9\%$). As can be seen in Table 8, for the elaboration and validation samples, the percentages of correct classification are higher than the C_{pro} and the C_{max} (more than 50%).

[Insert Table 8]

Table 9 shows that *popularity and promotional programs* is the factor that contributes the most to discriminating the segments in discriminant function 1, and *external and internal atmosphere* contributes most in discriminant function 2.

[Insert Table 9]

In summary, given the results of the different tests of hypothesis, criteria and values of the multiple discriminant analysis conducted on the segments of shopping centre consumers, we can conclude that the classification obtained from the factorial analysis and the analysis cluster is valid, as well as the classification capacity of the discriminant functions obtained. It can also be said that, as the factor analysis has shown, mall essence is the most important factor in attracting Mexican shoppers to a shopping centre. However, discriminant analysis revealed that promotional programs and external/internal atmosphere are the most important factors for differentiating between segments of consumers.

6. Conclusions and Implications

In Mexico, despite the constant growth of the shopping centre industry in the last several years, the empirical research hasn't been proportional. In this environment of shopping centre proliferation, shoppers have more options to select which shopping centre they prefer to visit and spend their time or money. In this sense, it is important to shopping centre administrators and retailers to know which components make shopping centres attractive to consumers. The first purpose of this study was to determine which components are included in shopping centre attractiveness from the point of view of the Mexican consumer. Secondly, previous research had discovered that not all shoppers are similar in their perceptions of attractiveness, thus segmentation could help to distinguish among different types of shoppers.

In terms to the first objective, the scale used has been useful in explaining perceptions of shopping centre attractiveness. Six dimensions were identified as relevant for the construction of attractiveness in Mexican shoppers. In this case, consistent with the empirical studies conducted by Reynolds et al. (2002) and Sit et al. (2003), *mall essence*, known in previous studies as the essence of offerings of the shopping centre, was the most important dimension in shopping centre attractiveness. The second most important was *popularity and promotional programs*. This dimension has some similarity with *sales incentives* and *popularity of the shopping centre* from Wong, et al.'s contribution (2001) and Rajagopal's (2009) economic variable called *sales and promotional*. In this particular study, *popularity and promotional programs* implies two specific aspects not considered before: advertising campaigns and loyalty programs. In third place, *personal service*, one of the big four presented by Sit et al. (2003), give to the shopping centre's personnel a significant role in the perception of the attractiveness of a shopping centre. The fourth dimension, *recreational offerings*, supports previous results (Reynolds et al., 2002; Sit et al., 2003; El-Adly, 2007) in which the shopping centre is perceived as a place not only for shopping but also for relaxation, entertainment and socialization. Finally, the last contribution to the perception of shopping centre attractiveness was *internal and external atmosphere*, also called by other authors *location and facilities* (Wong et al., 2001), *atmospherics and accessibility* (Sit et al., 2003) or *logistic related* (Rajagopal, 2009).

The first implication of these results has been to provide administrators an instrument to measure their shopping centre's performance and consequently to help them to define

marketing strategies focused on the aspects that are most significant in the perception of attractiveness from the consumer's point of view. In this sense, this instrument has been used to elaborate a positioning map with the six dimensions and the relative evaluation obtained by each of the five shopping centre participants. This map has offered helpful information about the competitive positioning strategy of shopping centres.

In addition, the scale has also been employed to segment shopping centres' consumers. Through a cluster analysis, three groups of consumers were found: serious, enthusiast, and basic. In order to highlight the coincidence of the profiles found between the Mexican shoppers and consumers of other nationalities, we decided to employ similar terminology for the segments. First, with respect to findings in other countries, in the case of Mexico only three consumer segments were found, similar to the proposal of El-Adly (2007). Of these three consumer segments, two are directly oriented toward the essence of the shopping centre and only one toward the more complete experience that implies socialization and entertainment, the enthusiast. Different from previous studies, in the case of the Mexican shopper, no group was found that was oriented only to entertainment. In addition, the differences in the types of activities carried out by each of the segments in the shopping centre were not significant. This permits us to assert that in general the Mexican consumer has multiple purposes in visiting a shopping centre, combining shopping, entertainment, and socialization, and that a segmentation based on attributes of shopping centre attractiveness is the most useful for administrators of shopping centres.

Shopping centre administrators should be conscious that some attributes have more relevance than others when it comes to attracting customers. In this sense, one of the most relevant results of this study is that for all shoppers, the essence of the shopping centre is the factor with the most weight when evaluating a shopping centre. What this means for administrators and store owners is that the offerings of different store types, brands, quality and prices should be studied carefully in order to satisfy all consumers. In addition, there are interesting differences with regard to other attractiveness factors according to the results of the cluster and discriminant analyses. These revealed that promotions and the internal and external atmosphere of shopping centres are the factors that can best help to differentiate the positioning of shopping centres with respect to their consumer segments.

The impact for shopping centre administrators is centred on the possibilities of focusing the strategies of the shopping centre on the expectations of its consumer segment. This is especially interesting in light of the significant differences found between segments and preferred shopping centres: *enthusiasts* toward lifestyle centres, *basic* toward community centres and *serious* toward regional centres.

Administrators of lifestyle centres should consider the characteristics of their consumer segment, *enthusiasts*. Enthusiasts are adults seeking a complete experience; they are frequent and demanding customers, as they consider the most factors when choosing a shopping centre. Creating diverse offerings and an attractive atmosphere could be the key for the strategic positioning of this category of shopping centre.

On the other hand, *basic* consumers are oriented toward convenience. They are mostly young women who find themselves attracted to the community centre. This is the segment that gives most relevance to the factor of external atmosphere, which includes location and access to the shopping centre, availability of parking, security in the shopping centre and the size of the shopping centre. Moreover, they are the most sensitive to internal elements related to decoration, amenities, and ambience. These results were also identified in the group sessions, in which women insisted on the relevance of parking and security in the shopping centre. The marketing strategy for community centre administrators is clear: focus on the above-mentioned aspects to be most attractive to this segment.

Serious consumer feel most attracted to regional centres; therefore administrators and store owners of these shopping centres should try to establish marketing strategies that position their shopping centre as that with the most varied offerings of brands, quality and price, without forgetting to give importance to the promotions and campaigns that make the shopping centre popular.

7. Study limitations and future research

This study contributes to the growing body of cross-national research on shopping centres by exploring attractiveness and consumer segments in Mexico. The consumer segments that were uncovered, and their profiling in terms of factor attractiveness, preference and demographic characteristics, are valuable and useful for local and international retailers who operate or are contemplating entry to the Mexican shopping centre industry. However,

one of the important limitations of this study is the possibility of generalizing the results to the national level, since in this case all 1500 surveys were conducted in the MAG. Looking toward the future, it would be relevant to replicate this study in other cities of Mexico, which, in addition to allowing a generalization at the national level, would make it possible to contrast the consumer segments by city.

As other researchers have shown (Wong et al., 2001; Adkins LeHew, Burgess, and Wesley, 2002; Anselmsson, 2006; Teller, 2008), future development of this research could be to measure the impact of shopping centre attractiveness on consumers' behaviour such as frequency of visits, relative spending, satisfaction or loyalty.

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